

DS-RAN-XAP: AI-Driven Dual Stage Explainable Anomaly Prediction for Beyond 5G Networks

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Abstract—In this work, we introduce Dual-Stage Radio Access Network eXplainable Anomaly Prediction (DS-RAN-XAP), a novel Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven and explainable framework for predictive Anomaly Detection (AD) in RAN environments. Designed to proactively monitor mobile connectivity, the framework integrates three key components: (i) multivariate time-series forecasting of network telemetry, (ii) connectivity classification between Radio Access Technologies (RATs), and (iii) unsupervised AD to detect degradations in network behavior. To ensure transparency and interpretability, the framework leverages SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to identify which Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) mostly affect AI model outputs. Evaluated on real-world multivariate RAN data, DS-RAN-XAP demonstrates strong performance across all stages. The classification component achieves an F1-score of up to 89.2%, while predictive classification retains high accuracy across medium and long-term forecasting horizons. The AD module, based on an Autoencoder (AE) architecture, achieves an F1-score of over 75% on forecasted data, validating its ability to generalize to future connectivity conditions. SHAP explainability further enhances model trust by offering insight into the KPIs contributing most to anomalous behavior. Thanks to its modular architecture, DS-RAN-XAP allows for flexible integration of alternative AI models at each stage. Thus, it supports deployment across diverse network infrastructures and operational objectives, aligning with the goal of predictive, explainable intelligence in next-generation mobile networks.

Index Terms—6G Networks, Radio Access Network, Channel Quality Metrics, Mobile User Equipment, Time Series Forecasting, Supervised Classification, Unsupervised Anomaly Detection, Explainable AI, SHAP

I. INTRODUCTION

The next generation of 5G wireless networks and the emerging 6G networks are poised to support a wide range of mission-critical and latency-sensitive applications, such as autonomous driving, cloud gaming, video streaming, eXtended Reality (XR), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and industrial automation [1]. In most of these scenarios, the quality and reliability of the mobile connection directly affect system performance and user safety. While significant research has been dedicated to optimizing throughput [2], latency [3], and mobility support, relatively less attention has been given to the ability to anticipate and explain future degradations in network quality, especially under real-world mobile conditions.

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In highly dynamic environments with moving User Equipment (UE) devices, such as vehicular networks, the mobile UE experiences rapid changes in Radio Access Network (RAN) conditions due to mobility, interference, cell-edge effects, and handovers. These conditions create the need for a robust framework that can predict short and medium-term channel quality evolution, detect anomalous behaviors in advance, and interpret the causes of such anomalies. Doing so can empower proactive decision making, such as route adaptation for autonomous vehicles [4], intelligent handover planning [5], or predictive Quality of Service (QoS) management [6].

Recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have shown promise in addressing complex data-driven problems in wireless communications [7]. AI-driven approaches are well-positioned to perform multivariate analysis on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) collected from mobile UEs, including time-series forecasting [8] and evaluation of channel conditions, allowing for real-time predictions and automatic fault detection. Thus, AI integration has become a compelling solution to address the challenges of dynamic mobile network environments.

The main question this work aims to answer is whether we can use AI models trained on real-world UE metrics to predict the future quality of wireless connectivity accurately. This involves evaluating how well future channel KPIs can be predicted from past trends, determining if these predictions are trustworthy enough for tasks like Anomaly Detection (AD), and identifying significant deviations from expected connectivity in a fully unsupervised and explainable manner. These challenges are especially relevant in the context of 6G systems, where predictable and explainable mobile link performance is critical to ensuring safety and service continuity.

To address the aforementioned challenges, we propose a novel Dual-Stage RAN eXplainable Anomaly Prediction (DS-RAN-XAP) framework tailored for 5G/6G-connected mobile systems and validated using real-world data. At its core, DS-RAN-XAP combines three complementary AI-driven processes: forecasting of UE-side RAN telemetry to determine future channel conditions, explainable classification of connection quality to capture upcoming network states, and unsupervised AD to proactively flag network connectivity deviations from normal behavior. The main novelty of DS-RAN-XAP lies in the unified and modular integration of these processes into a single, end-to-end framework that enables explainable and predictive anomaly prediction under realistic RAN conditions. Explainability across the classification and AD stages is provided through

Fig. 1. High-level schematic of DS-RAN-XAP, illustrating the flow of KPI telemetry from the UEs to the framework, and the delivery of explainable anomaly outputs to network operators and users.

the SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [9] algorithm, allowing for interpretable analysis of connectivity and offering actionable insights. Fig. 1 presents a high-level schematic of the DS-RAN-XAP framework. As depicted, the resulting XAP output, comprising detected anomalies in RAN connectivity and their feature-based explanations, is delivered to both network operators and end-user devices, ensuring transparency across the network stack. The figure highlights the framework's role in bridging the gap between today's 5G systems and future 6G networks. By embedding AI automation and explainability directly into downstream tasks, such as connection quality identification and anomaly prediction, DS-RAN-XAP provides proactive and trustworthy network intelligence. Additionally, by considering real-world system data, we are able to determine the viability of our approach in a practical context. By combining these elements, the framework provides a predictive and interpretable approach to mobile connectivity analysis, leading to the following key contributions of this work:

- We propose a unified framework for explainable anomaly prediction of mobile network quality, integrating time-series forecasting, classification, and AD.
- We introduce a dual-stage modeling approach that first characterizes normal and degraded connectivity through classification and explainability, and then applies these insights to guide the unsupervised AD process.
- We provide end-to-end explainability through SHAP integration at both stages, enabling root-cause analysis and transparent decision support for operators and users.
- We validate the effectiveness of our approach by utilizing a real-world UE-side dataset collected from a commercial network, ensuring the framework's practical relevance and real-world applicability.
- We provide an extensive performance evaluation across multiple forecasting and classification models and varying prediction horizons, demonstrating both the robustness of downstream tasks on forecasted data

and the modularity of the overall approach for diverse deployment scenarios.

The rest of our paper is structured as follows: Section II outlines relevant state-of-the-art works that focus on predictive downstream tasks, identification of anomalous connectivity, and interpretable AD, based on metrics derived from the RAN domain. Section III presents the overall architecture of the proposed framework and the main workflows and components it comprises. Section IV describes the dataset selected for evaluation and the main preprocessing steps. In Sections V, VI, and VII, we analyze the three main processes, namely the forecasting, classification, and AD components, respectively. Each of these sections includes both the methodology and experimental results for each specific process. Finally, Section VIII provides conclusions and future research directions for this work.

II. RELATED WORK

Several recent works explored ML and AI-based techniques in wireless communications for network performance prediction, AD, and explainability. These works focus on specific problems within the RAN domain, such as signal strength estimation, event-specific fault detection, or throughput prediction, studying these as isolated challenges. In this section, we present a review of representative studies spanning these research directions.

Work based on RAN signal modeling has focused on the prediction of key channel quality indicators, often using supervised learning models of radio coverage to estimate the signal levels, while also relying on environmental or location data. The authors of [10] use ML models to predict radio signal strength for network planning using simulated transmitter placement data. They show that simple models like K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) can achieve high accuracy, enabling fast and reliable coverage estimation. In [11], the authors develop and evaluate ML models for Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) prediction, using a large real-world dataset. They compare a multitude of algorithms across diverse environments and frequency bands, evaluating accuracy and computational efficiency. Random Forest (RF) is identified as a practical choice for accurate and efficient mobile coverage prediction. Nevertheless, these works are limited to static signal-level modeling and do not extend to proactive or explainable anomaly prediction, making them unsuitable for dynamic 6G use cases.

Building on signal-level indicators, several works have tackled the challenge of throughput forecasting using physical-layer and RAN metrics. They often rely on time-series forecasting or lightweight filtering for predicting Uplink (UL) or Downlink (DL) performance over short-term horizons. Reference [12] proposes a lightweight method for predicting 5G throughput based on the use of multiple linear regression and Kalman filtering. The combination allows measurement and prediction noise to be incorporated explicitly, leading to accurate, low-latency predictions. The approach delivers superior responsiveness and Quality of Experience (QoE) compared to ML baselines, and is therefore suitable for real-time applications with limited

resources. The work of [13] highlights the rising importance of UL prediction for emerging Internet of Things (IoT) and emergency response applications. It introduces an ML-based UL throughput prediction model, using mobile network data collected across diverse environments. The model operates off of lower-layer radio metrics (Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ), and RSRP), and a comparison of ML algorithms finds decision trees and KNN performed the best. An ML and Deep Learning-based framework is proposed in [14] to forecast UE DL throughput on Long-Term Evolution (LTE) networks. It uses a seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average model to forecast DL Physical Resource Block (PRB) utilization, PRB availability, and DL traffic, metrics that are found to mostly impact the UE DL throughput. These indicators are next used as inputs in a neural network regression model that predicts DL throughput, thus enhancing the efficiency of mobile network planning. While effective for throughput-centric tasks, these approaches remain narrow in scope, focusing on traffic prediction without extending to AD or explainability.

A parallel line of research focuses on predicting specific types of network anomalies, such as abnormal traffic, handovers, radio link failures, and QoE drops in multimedia streaming. The framework presented in [15] is designed to identify anomalous events like flash crowds in mobile data traffic. It leverages Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to learn the temporal context of input sequences from real traffic traces of a commercial network, achieving higher performance compared to classic AD algorithms. Reference [16] tackles real-time bandwidth and handoff prediction for 4G and 5G networks using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) based models and Gradient Boosting. The method is applied to fixed-route mobility use cases, accurately predicting 80% of handoffs. A hybrid model based on LSTM networks and Support Vector Machines (SVM) is presented in [17] for Radio Link Failure (RLF) prediction. The LSTM model forecasts radio KPIs, which are then used as input to the SVM classifier, which determines the connection status with a 98% accuracy. Also focused on RLF prediction, [18] develops an LSTM-based Autoencoder (AE) model using weather forecast information in addition to network KPIs to capture spatiotemporal correlations. The method improved prediction accuracy and highlighted the potential of integrating environmental context to help proactively mitigate failures. The works [19] and [20] use low-level wireless metrics to tackle QoE prediction for video streaming in mobile networks. The focus of [19] is video stall prediction for different mobility contexts, achieving 90% prediction accuracy by training ML models on time series windows. In [20], a two-stage transformer framework is designed to improve application-layer QoE prediction performance in a wireless video transmission system, significantly reducing the prediction Mean Absolute Error (MAE). Despite their predictive capability, these solutions are tailored to specific anomaly types and lack a generalized, explainable framework that can operate across diverse RAN conditions.

Finally, few efforts have explored explainability as part

of the AD process in the RAN domain, often leveraging AEs and focusing on interpretability through SHAP values, feedback loops, or attention mechanisms. For instance, [21] introduced a distributed explainable AD system for 5G Open-RAN. It used two efficient generative models deployed at edge resources to detect abnormalities and reduce false alarms. The system minimized bandwidth and computation overhead, and outperformed baseline implementations in both accuracy and interpretability. Reference [22] proposed XAIomaly, a framework devised for low-latency use cases on Open-RAN infrastructure. A deep AE model was deployed as an xApp, achieving 93% accuracy when tested on UE device data. A newly devised efficient XAI method based on SHAP, called fastSHAP-C, was integrated within the framework to explain the AE's decisions, and also improved resource utilization by 25%, making it ideal for real-time scenarios. The authors of [23] also leveraged a combination of a sparse AE and the SHAP algorithm to identify and interpret anomalies in RAN cell traces. For each anomalous trace, their approach correlated features with high reconstruction errors to other features that contributed to this error, offering further insight for effective root cause analysis. The previous work is further expanded upon in [24], where a feedback loop is integrated with a cluster-characterized AE framework. This design removes features with minimal impact on the AD process, thus improving overall efficiency and performance, while at the same time offering concise explanations to the end user. Although these works incorporate explainability, they do not integrate forecasting or predictive capabilities, which are crucial for proactive network management.

While the previous works have contributed advancements across individual research directions, including KPI forecasting, task-specific failure prediction, and explainable AD, they have predominantly addressed these challenges in isolation or in task-oriented combinations. As summarized in Table I, most existing approaches either focus on reactive AD applied to observed RAN KPIs or on forecasting performance metrics without extending them to generalized anomaly prediction. Furthermore, works that incorporate predictive capabilities typically target specific anomalous events (e.g., RLF, handovers, or QoE degradation) rather than modeling anomalous behavior at the level of overall RAN connectivity in a task-agnostic manner. In parallel, several studies have introduced explainability within RAN AD pipelines; however, these approaches remain reactive and are not coupled with forecasting-aware anomaly prediction. In contrast, the proposed DS-RAN-XAP framework integrates multivariate RAN KPI forecasting with anomaly prediction and explainable analysis in a unified, task-agnostic, connectivity-based anomaly modeling design, enabling proactive and interpretable RAN management in beyond-5G environments.

III. DS-RAN-XAP FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

This section delves into the main components of the DS-RAN-XAP framework and analyzes the core workflows. Fig. 2 depicts the internal system architecture and the

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF REPRESENTATIVE RAN-ORIENTED AI PIPELINES. THE TABLE HIGHLIGHTS THE DISTINCTION BETWEEN REACTIVE AD APPLIED TO OBSERVED KPIS AND FORECASTING-AWARE ANOMALY PREDICTION, AS WELL AS THE PREVALENCE OF TASK-SPECIFIC VERSUS TASK-AGNOSTIC ANOMALY MODELING. IT FURTHER ILLUSTRATES THE LIMITED INTEGRATION OF OPERATIONAL EXPLAINABILITY WITHIN PREDICTIVE ARCHITECTURES IN EXISTING WORKS.

Work	RAN KPI Forecasting	Anomaly Detection on Observed RAN KPIS	Anomaly Prediction on Forecasted RAN KPIS	Operational Explainability	Task-Agnostic Connectivity-based Anomaly Modeling
Signal / Throughput KPI Forecasting [10]– [14]	✓	×	×	×	×
Task-Specific Failure / Event Prediction [15]– [20]	✓	✓	✓	×	×
RAN Explainable Anomaly Detection [21]– [24]	×	✓	×	✓	✓
DS-RAN-XAP (This Work)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

interactions between the major components, which are the data preparation block, the forecasting block, and the two AI-enabled processing stages with explainable outputs towards relevant stakeholders.

First, during the data preparation process, the radio KPIS and UE mobility information are ingested by the system and preprocessed so that they can be used as input for the ML models. Apart from data cleaning and labeling, the main processing is centered on organizing the multivariate data into non-overlapping time series windows, so they can be effectively leveraged by the time series forecasting model. The preprocessing is examined in detail in the next section.

Continuing, the architecture comprises three AI-based components, namely the forecasting, network mode characterization, and unsupervised AD blocks. Following the data preparation, these blocks support two possible workflows:

- 1) **Direct Anomaly Detection workflow:** In direct mode, the input KPI window is directly connected to the dual-stage classification and AD downstream pipeline, and the forecaster is not used. This workflow enables explainable detection of connectivity issues using the streaming metrics from the UE but does not involve predictive modeling.
- 2) **Forecasting-aware Anomaly Prediction workflow:** To allow for proactive decision making and mitigation of connectivity issues, this main workflow of DS-RAN-XAP is enabled by time series forecasting. In this case, the window is first used as input for the forecasting model, which outputs a corresponding predicted window of a predetermined length of timesteps, namely the forecasting horizon. The predicted window is then processed through the same two-stage pipeline as in the direct workflow. By facilitating detection across future samples, the framework is equipped to allow for mitigating actions like early fault warning, UE mobility decisions, and predictive allocation of radio resources. Overall, this workflow directly addresses forecasting-aware anomaly prediction at the RAN connectivity level, as also highlighted in Table I.

Supporting both workflows covers a broader set of operational demands. The first workflow offers more accurate outputs, as it leverages the real collected data, making it

fitting for runtime fault monitoring and root cause analysis. The predictive mode may likely incur lower accuracy due to the uncertainty associated with the forecasting step, however, it offers valuable lead time for proactive handovers, route adaptation for moving UEs, or other application adjustments based on QoS considerations. Furthermore, the two options allow operators and users to balance accuracy and responsiveness based on resource constraints, low-latency application requirements, and confidence in the forecasting horizon. This dual-workflow design is a key architectural contribution of our framework, as it allows the same downstream anomaly prediction and explainability pipeline to operate seamlessly on both observed and forecasted data, enabling proactive RAN management without redesigning the underlying system.

Continuing with the dual-stage pipeline, as showcased in Fig. 2, in the first stage, we use supervised classifiers to infer the network mode from the input KPI samples, which provides a high-level but actionable indicator of connection quality. To support both interpretability and downstream anomaly modeling decisions, SHAP is integrated at this stage as an explainability mechanism that provides global and local feature attributions. Global SHAP analysis is employed on the classifier to identify the most important features (e.g., high Channel Quality Indicator (CQI), RSRP) most strongly associated with high-quality connectivity. Rather than serving solely as an explanation tool, the resulting SHAP outputs are leveraged to guide the definition of the normal connectivity samples used for training the AE model in the subsequent anomaly prediction stage. This establishes SHAP as a computational link between the two stages of the pipeline, enabling explainability-driven anomaly distribution modeling. Further methodological details of this process of defining a high-quality dataset for the unsupervised AD task are provided in Section VII.

Consequently, in the second stage, we deploy an unsupervised AE trained solely on these high-quality samples, enabling the identification of abnormal connection through high reconstruction errors. Again, SHAP is applied to the AE, but with a focus on providing local explanations, in order to get feature importance insights on the specific detected anomalous samples. By coupling these stages DS-

Fig. 2. Architecture and Workflow Diagram of the DS-RAN-XAP framework, outlining the main building blocks: Data Preparation, RAN KPI Forecasting, and the Dual-Stage pipeline. These components enable reactive AD on observed KPIs, as well as forecasting-aware, connectivity-based anomaly prediction. Explainability is integrated operationally via SHAP, supporting both the modeling of normal connectivity behavior and the interpretation of anomaly prediction outcomes for operators and end users.

RAN-XAP forms a cohesive end-to-end system, ensuring that outputs from each component are directly leveraged by subsequent processes. In contrast to existing forecasting-based approaches in the RAN domain that do not integrate explainability, our framework operationally integrates SHAP to support anomaly modeling and to provide interpretable outputs to key recipients, including: (i) Network operators who can understand the root-cause of connectivity problems and adjust RAN behavior accordingly, (ii) UE devices, which can adapt application logic or mobility patterns according to predicted degradations, (iii) UE users, who receive timely information about application-side issues, (e.g., streaming video lag), preserving high QoE. The final output of the framework consists of flags of anomalous samples, predicted connection states, and SHAP-based feature importance plots, which can be made available to all stakeholders, ensuring transparency, reliability, and actionable insights.

On a final note, it is important to highlight the overall modularity of the framework. In each AI-enabled process, various fitting forecasting, classification, or AD models can be tested and used, based on which one performs best. This modular design is particularly important in the RAN domain, where network dynamics and data characteristics may vary, and no single model can always be assumed to be universally optimal. The model-agnostic nature of

SHAP is critical in preserving explainability consistency and guiding anomaly modeling across this modular architecture, ensuring that operational insights remain valid irrespective of the specific models employed. The above are evidenced in the comparative analysis in the next sections, allowing the framework to adapt for different network configurations and use cases. Building on this, the following sections provide a detailed description of each architectural stage, including methodology, implementation, and experimental evaluation.

IV. DATASET AND PREPROCESSING

This section presents the dataset used for testing and validating our framework, along with the preprocessing steps applied to prepare the data for the forecasting and AD processes. We choose to present the preprocessing details upfront, since all main processes of the framework rely on the same prepared data. This also aligns with the architecture in Fig. 2, where Data Preparation is the first building block of the pipeline and provides the basis for the evaluation that follows. While our framework is directly extensible to beyond-5G and 6G systems, we employ an available commercial 5G dataset to assess its operational viability in a realistic setting. Specifically, we employ the dataset introduced in [25], which is an open-source production dataset collected from a 5G operator, for driving and

static scenarios. In our analysis, we leverage the samples of the driving scenario, as they offer higher complexity in UE connectivity and mobility patterns.

The selected dataset includes mobility metrics, channel quality indicators, and throughput data, captured from a smartphone UE device at 1-second granularity, while the UE is running two types of applications, video streaming and file download. We select this dataset as it accurately reflects real-world mobile behavior, making it suitable for validating device-side analytics frameworks like DS-RAN-XAP. Table II showcases the subset of relevant KPIs selected for training and evaluating the proposed framework, while the Coefficient of Variation (CoV) is also computed for each feature to assess its relative volatility. The CoV is leveraged to enhance the experimental results analysis in Section V. The *NetworkMode* variable is only used for labeling part of the dataset for the connectivity classification stage. We also note that, while the dataset does provide the serving cell ID for each sample, we exclude it to avoid model overfitting to the specific commercial network infrastructure, and instead aim to generalize across cell deployments by relying only on location and speed features, along with the channel metrics.

TABLE II

SELECTED KPIs USED IN THE DS-RAN-XAP FRAMEWORK AND COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION (COV) FOR EACH KPI

KPI (Unit)	Specification	CoV (%)
Longitude (°)	Geographic Longitude	0.49
Latitude (°)	Geographic Latitude	0.03
Speed (km/h)	User Equipment Speed	61.88
RSRP (dBm)	Reference Signal Received Power	15.82
RSRQ (dB)	Reference Signal Received Quality	43.38
SNR (dB)	Signal-to-Noise Ratio	231.78
CQI (0–15)	Channel Quality Indicator	34.05
RSSI (dBm)	Received Signal Strength Indicator	16.06
DL_bitrate (Mbps)	Downlink Bitrate	408.91
UL_bitrate (Mbps)	Uplink Bitrate	477.69
NRxRSRP (dBm)	Neighboring Cell RSRP	22.92
NRxRSRQ (dB)	Neighboring Cell RSRQ	178.01
Network Mode (4G/5G)	Type of Connectivity (used for labeling)	N/A

As is typical for various types of system and channel monitoring in mobile networks [26], the collected KPIs are structured as a Multivariate Time Series (MTS), where each time step represents a vector of values across all selected features. Formally, the multivariate time series can be represented as:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = [x_t^{(1)}, x_t^{(2)}, \dots, x_t^{(n)}]^T, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_t is the feature vector at time step t , $x_t^{(i)}$ is the value of the i -th KPI at time t , n is the total number of KPIs, and T is the total number of time steps. These sequences exhibit temporal dependencies between features, which can be learned by ML and deep learning models during training to enable accurate forecasting of future timesteps. To prepare the dataset for training and evaluation of the DS-RAN-XAP framework, the following preprocessing steps are applied:

- **Missing Value Handling:** We first remove samples with multiple null features or long data segments with null features. For sparse missing values, we apply the spline interpolation imputation method [27], which fits smooth polynomial curves between known data points to produce continuous estimates. Our testing confirmed that this approach offered slightly better results for the ML processes, compared to simpler imputation techniques like mean imputation, forward fill, or linear interpolation.
- **Normalization:** All KPI values are scaled to the range $[0, 1]$ using min-max normalization, to ensure uniform contribution of all features during training.
- **Rolling Window Construction:** The normalized MTS data, as defined in (1), is split into non-overlapping input-output window pairs for supervised sequence learning. Each input window consists of L (denoted so for "Lookback" or "Lag" samples) past time steps, and the corresponding output window contains the subsequent H (denoted so for forecasting "Horizon" samples) steps to be predicted. The specific values of L and H selected for training and evaluation are reported in Section V. For a given window index j , we define:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}^{(j)} = [\mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{x}_{j+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{j+L-1}] \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{out}}^{(j)} = [\mathbf{x}_{j+L}, \mathbf{x}_{j+L+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{j+L+H-1}] \quad (3)$$

These windows form training pairs for supervised learning:

$$(\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}^{(j)}, \mathbf{X}_{\text{out}}^{(j)}) \in (\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}, \mathbf{X}_{\text{out}}) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{X}_{in} and \mathbf{X}_{out} are the full collections of input and output sequences, respectively. These pairs allow the model to learn mappings from past KPI dynamics to future network behavior.

Training and inference via sliding or rolling window pairs, which is the approach we use in our framework, is commonly encountered in AI pipelines [28], especially for MTS data. In deployment scenarios within which UE KPI samples are being continuously provided and streamed, this approach provides the model with the most recent metrics for inference. At the operational level, using fixed-length, non-overlapping windows is even more efficient and scalable in production environments, and thus, is a commonly adopted strategy for real-time frameworks in mobile networks [16], [29]. Instead of performing continuous inference on high-frequency data streams, systems can report and process discrete windows at meaningful intervals. This reduces computational burden and allows for better synchronization of monitoring and inference, while also supporting a steady integration of AI-enabled decision making into real-time control loops.

V. RAN KPI FORECASTING PROCESS

In this Section, we analyze the forecasting process used to predict the previously defined RAN metrics, which will enable the two-stage predictive workflows of the following Sections. We first present the relevant methodology, and subsequently provide the experimental evaluation results.

A. Methodology

ML and deep learning approaches have been widely used for forecasting tasks in wireless networks, particularly in the RAN domain. As outlined in Section II, tasks like throughput prediction and signal strength estimation have employed a variety of AI model types. These include classic autoregressive models, like Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average and Vector Autoregression (VAR) [14], [30], tree-based methods like RF and XGBoost [13], [31], LSTM deep learning architectures [16], [17], [18], [32], [33], and, more recently, Transformer architectures [20].

Motivated by the range of techniques employed in prior works, this paper provides a comparative analysis by deploying representative models from these paradigms in the forecasting pipeline of the framework to predict KPI sequences. Our goal is to assess the trade-offs between forecasting accuracy, model complexity, and adaptability in the RAN context. Specifically, the models we deploy and compare are:

- **Vector Autoregression Model (VAR):** VAR is a linear approach tailored for stationary MTS data that captures dynamic relationships and interdependencies across multiple variables. We select VAR as a forecasting benchmark solution, given its simplicity and very low computational cost.
- **XGBoost (XGB):** XGBoost [34] is a tree-based gradient boosting algorithm mostly applied to classification and regression tasks. To effectively utilize XGBoost for sequence forecasting, we flatten each of the input-output rolling window pairs and formulate the prediction task as a supervised regression problem. The main advantages of this model are speed and scalability.
- **LSTM Encoder-Decoder:** We devise and test an LSTM-based architecture that comprises an encoder with one LSTM layer and a symmetrical decoder. The encoder maps the input KPIs into a lower-dimensional latent space to extract temporal patterns between variables, like the change of signal strength KPIs over time, or how location and speed may influence metrics like SNR and CQI. The decoder, based on this mapping, generates the predicted output sequence. This model is selected because, as showcased in prior works referenced above, LSTM-based solutions have achieved superior performance in predicting sequences that exhibit nonlinear complex patterns, like RAN mobility and signal dynamics.
- **Patch-based Time Series Transformer (PatchTST):** PatchTST [35] is a recent neural network architecture that uses Transformers for efficient and accurate forecasting across longer horizons. The model processes the data as a set of non-overlapping temporal patches, which are consecutive data blocks of fixed size. Each patch is treated as a token, and the self-attention mechanism is applied across the patches, instead of individual timesteps. This design reduces the sequence length, limiting computational complexity. The patching mechanism is advantageous when applied to 5G

KPI sequences, as it allows capturing both local dynamics, like sharp drops in signal quality, and long-range dependencies, like how various mobility trends may affect throughput. This mechanism is also beneficial for modeling longer sequences, which is critical for predictive tasks involving extended prediction horizons in time-sensitive applications like handover planning or anomaly prediction. In addition, the reduced attention space also reduces the risk of overfitting, something that classic Transformers are prone to in noisy telemetry data collected from real-world wireless systems. The aforementioned advantages support adapting this model to real-time monitoring pipelines for RAN, where accuracy and efficiency are equally important.

- **Inverted Transformer (iTransformer):** iTransformer [36] is another recent Transformer-based architecture that inverts the traditional approach by embedding the time points of individual series as variate tokens. Self-attention operates across variates, while the feed-forward network models temporal representations for each token. This design enhances performance and efficiency on datasets with complex multivariate correlations and scales to longer lookback windows.

The utilization of PatchTST and iTransformer within our framework to model 5G KPI sequences constitute some of the first applications of these recent models in the RAN domain. The comparative evaluation that follows in this section provides practically valuable insights, highlighting trade-offs in handling RAN-specific dynamics across extended horizons. To train and test the models, we frame the forecasting problem as a supervised multivariate sequence-to-sequence task, where the model learns a mapping from an input window of past KPI values to a future window of the same KPIs. For this purpose, we use the rolling windows defined in Section IV. Each input window $\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}}^{(j)}$ contains L past timesteps and the corresponding prediction target $\mathbf{X}_{\text{out}}^{(j)}$ contains the next H future steps, thus the final shapes of input and output windows are:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times L \times n} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times n} \quad (6)$$

where W is the total number of non-overlapping windows and n is the number of KPIs. The forecasting horizon is selected as $H = 120$, which is a 2-minute prediction window based on the granularity of the dataset.

Contrary to previous works that typically consider shorter horizons [16], [17], we explore medium and long-term forecasts, which can be valuable for proactive decision-making tasks in 5G and emerging 6G networks, like predictive handovers [16], stall prediction [19], or predictive caching [37] in edge applications. Most importantly, by analyzing longer horizons, we will assess the degree of effectiveness for leveraging the forecasted KPI sequences in our framework's dual-stage AD processes, to determine how far ahead reliable inference can be performed within the DS-RAN-XAP pipeline.

After forming the training sequences, the forecasting models are all trained to minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss across all windows, defined as:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N \cdot H \cdot n} \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\hat{x}_{j,t+h}^{(i)} - x_{j,t+h}^{(i)} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where N is the total number of prediction windows, H is the forecasting horizon, n is the number of KPIs, $\hat{x}_{j,t+h}^{(i)}$ is the predicted value of the i -th KPI at time $t+h$ in window j , and $x_{j,t+h}^{(i)}$ is the ground truth value of the i -th KPI at time $t+h$ in window j . We specifically select the MSE loss due to its sensitivity to outliers. While other works smooth or remove outliers to improve forecasting accuracy, we explicitly aim to preserve and forecast such deviations in the data. This is essential for the network mode classification and AD tasks, for which we need to retain and detect the irregular patterns in the data, through which we identify abnormal connectivity conditions.

B. Experimental Setup and Results

After we apply all preprocessing steps, we extract 89443 total samples at 1s granularity from the original dataset. For $H = 120$ and with a 60%-40% train-test split we form a total of $W_{\text{train}} = 446$ input-output rolling window pairs for the training set and $N_{\text{test}} = 297$ input-output pairs for the testing set, respectively. The validation data is defined as 10% of the total training samples. The forecasting models are trained and evaluated on these windows.

The experimental setup for training each model is as follows. For VAR, we first perform an Augmented Dickey-Fuller test [38] on the data, which confirms stationarity. The algorithm is then trained using 120 input lags. The XGBoost model is trained with the histogram-based tree method, with 500 estimators, a maximum depth of 5, a learning rate of 0.1, and the MSE loss. Early stopping is applied with 10 rounds. For the LSTM architecture, its encoder and symmetrical decoder comprise one LSTM layer with 64 neurons each. The model is trained for 100 epochs with the Adam optimizer [39], learning rate of 0.001, and MSE loss. Early stopping is also applied. Next, PatchTST is trained with the following internal parameters: patch_length=16, patch_stride=8, d_model=64, num_hidden_layers=3, head_dropout=0.1, dropout=0.1, and num_attention_heads=4. The optimizer is Adam with a learning rate of 0.0001 and the loss is the MSE. The model is trained for 100 epochs and early stopping is applied. Finally, the parameters for the best performing iTransformer model are: num_variates=12, lookback_len=120, pred_length=120, dim=256, depth=1, heads=4, dim_head=64, attn_dropout=0.2, ff_dropout=0.2. The model is trained for 200 epochs with the Adam optimizer, learning rate of 0.01, MSE loss and early stopping.

For the evaluation of the models, we calculate the MAE across all test set windows, as follows:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N \cdot H \cdot n} \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \hat{x}_{j,t+h}^{(i)} - x_{j,t+h}^{(i)} \right| \quad (8)$$

Features with lower CoV exhibit steadier patterns and are generally easier to forecast, while highly volatile features present greater forecasting challenges. We train and test all models for $L = 120$ and $H = 120$. Table III displays the average MAE (in the original unit of measure of each KPI) across the forecasting horizon, for the 12 KPIs. The model ranks (1)-(5) indicate training speed.

TABLE III
FORECASTING MAE FOR EACH KPI. MODEL RANKS (1)-(5) INDICATE TRAINING SPEED.

KPI	MAE				
	VAR (1)	LSTM (5)	XGB (4)	PatchTST (2)	iTransformer (3)
Longitude	0.004	0.010	0.006	0.005	0.006
Latitude	0.002	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.003
Speed	11.811	12.414	12.296	10.187	10.519
RSRP	7.300	8.731	7.853	7.584	7.813
RSRQ	2.482	3.116	2.844	2.481	2.521
SNR	6.135	6.608	6.227	5.976	5.972
CQI	2.430	2.565	2.564	2.379	2.4
RSSI	7.109	7.125	7.427	6.974	7.008
DL_bitrate	5.712	10.127	4.939	1.496	10.920
UL_bitrate	0.048	0.131	0.053	0.044	0.158
NRxRSRP	9.189	11.937	10.517	8.755	9.116
NRxRSRQ	15.425	16.404	15.071	17.252	18.826

Based on the results of our comparative analysis, we derive that the models demonstrate comparable performance, with the exception of DL_bitrate, where PatchTST clearly outperforms other models. VAR, despite its simplicity, outperforms more complex models on some variables, while also being the fastest, making it a solid baseline choice if efficiency is prioritized. PatchTST achieves the lowest MAE for the majority of KPIs, confirming its effectiveness in learning the temporal dependencies of RAN metrics, also outperforming the more recent iTransformer. This can be justified by the low average absolute correlation across KPIs (measured to be 0.1302), making PatchTST's univariate-focused patching more appropriate compared to iTransformer that is tailored for strong multivariate correlations. PatchTST ranks second in terms of training speed, while iTransformer ranks third, primarily due to the higher parameter count of its evaluated configuration. Overall, we will utilize the forecasted windows PatchTST produces for the predictive tasks in the dual-stage pipeline of our framework, as it balances strong performance, evidenced by our evaluation, and efficiency, which is crucial for deployment in resource-constrained 5G and 6G systems.

Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that no model is universally superior for all variables, with performance varying across KPIs. This variability further reinforces the modular design of our framework. Its modularity allows seamless integration and evaluation of various forecasters, ensuring future-proof adaptability to changing network dynamics and constantly improving forecasting models, to enable effective downstream anomaly prediction.

To further complement our analysis, we also separately calculate the average MAE of PatchTST for each timestep of the prediction horizon across all testing rolling windows.

Fig. 3. Forecasting MAE results for PatchTST across all timesteps of the forecasting horizon for all KPIs. The values of the MAE have been averaged for each specific timestep across all testing windows.

The results are depicted in Fig. 3 and offer an informative visualization of how the forecasting accuracy is affected by the value of H . As expected, while the horizon increases, the accuracy decreases for most KPIs, indicating the difficulty of predicting longer sequences. For KPIs with very high CoV, the MAE does not follow a specific pattern, showcasing the impact of the high volatility and unpredictability of their values on the forecasting capability of the tested models.

All in all, this section evaluates the viability of medium-term forecasting in the RAN domain with real-world data, and also produces the forecasted windows that are leveraged in the Forecasting-Aware Anomaly Prediction workflow of the following sections. This step is crucial, as it enables the framework to predict connectivity conditions rather than only react to past measurements. By doing so, it provides the necessary input for proactive AD, allowing operators and devices to identify and mitigate potential degradations before they manifest, which is of particular importance for reliability- and latency-critical 6G applications. Building on these forecasts, the following sections present the AD stages, where both ground-truth and forecasted KPI windows are analyzed to proactively identify deviations from normal behavior.

VI. STAGE 1: EXPLAINABLE CONNECTION STATE CLASSIFICATION

This Section focuses on the first part of the dual-stage DS-RAN-XAP pipeline, which is the explainable network mode classification. We first detail the methodology, including AI model selection and SHAP integration, and then present the experimental results using the groundtruth and forecasted test datasets.

A. Methodology

In this stage of the framework, we develop a supervised, explainable classification process to identify the connectivity state of the UE. By using true and predicted RAN KPIs, we enable interpretable, real-time, as well as predictive evaluation of connection quality, which plays an important role in network optimization and orchestration across different Radio Access Technologies (RATs). To address practical network planning, we define a binary classification case to distinguish between connection modes (e.g., 5G and 4G) using the *NetworkMode* variable for labeling.

In the context of beyond 5G and 6G, the capability to distinguish between connection modes in an interpretable manner is particularly important, as networks will need to autonomously adapt to rapidly changing conditions while

supporting diverse applications with strict reliability and latency demands. Identifying such transitions in advance is of high operational significance to enable adaptive QoS provisioning. For example, from the perspective of crucial UE-side use cases, predicting a connection downgrade in the near future can enable early video buffering for streaming applications [19] or handover planning for autonomous vehicle navigation [5], [40].

One of the main novelties of this classification process within the dual-stage pipeline is the forecasting-aware workflow. To evaluate the classification, apart from using the true target windows that were also used for testing the forecasting models in Section V, we also utilize the output windows forecasted by the PatchTST model. These two sets of windows are of the same shape $W \times H \times n$, and will be denoted as \mathbf{X}_{out} and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{out}}$, for the true and predicted windows, respectively. Each window set offers a total of $W \times H$ distinct samples of n KPIs, which allows us to directly compare the performance of the classification models for both the direct and predictive workflows. Further, evaluation across the prediction horizon provides insight into how far into the future connection state can still be inferred with reliable accuracy, as will be discussed in Section VI-B.

To benchmark performance for various modeling paradigms, we train different types of supervised classifiers that have been used in previous works for classification tasks in this domain [19], [41], [42], [43]. Specifically, we select Logistic Regression (LR), RF, XGBoost, LightGBM (LGBM) [44], Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Convolutional Neural Network Classifier (CNN) as the leveraged models compared for classification. These models represent a wide range of computational complexity, from simple linear classifiers to tree-based methods and neural network architectures, allowing us to account for trade-offs in terms of accuracy and computational complexity.

SHAP Integration: Moving on to the explainability aspect of this classification task, SHAP [9] is a key enabler integrated within the dual-stage pipeline of the framework. SHAP is a model-agnostic, post-model XAI method that is based on the game theory concept of Shapley Values. Its strong theoretical background allows robust feature attribution analysis, and consequent anomaly modeling within our framework. It provides feature importance explanations by determining how input features contribute to the value of output features. Through SHAP, an importance score for each feature can be calculated, showing its impact on the prediction for a specific input instance. The Python SHAP library is equipped with visualization capabilities, further enhancing the explanations.

Through SHAP, we can offer both local (referring to a single prediction) and global (aggregated across all samples) explanations, which are equally valuable within our framework. Local explanations allow for detailed, human-readable interpretation of why a sample was classified in a specific connectivity mode, providing actionable diagnostics for either network operators or intelligent agents making UE-side decisions. For example, explainable connection state classification can help an autonomous vehicle under-

stand why its link is degrading and whether a handover to a different RAT is imminent. This transparency allows user trust in the automated pipeline and enables debugging of misclassifications or identification of KPIs that exhibit anomalies in different locations or contexts.

Global explanations indicate which KPIs most influence model decisions of each connectivity class. These insights can be used to profile site-specific network behavior, identify dominant KPIs, and verify assumptions about network topology or propagation conditions. Further, the KPI patterns that SHAP identifies as strong indicators of high-quality connectivity are used to define the normal class of training data for our unsupervised AD model described in the next Section.

All in all, this stage connects raw KPI telemetry with higher-level, interpretable predictions of network quality. By leveraging accurate classification along with global and local interpretability, both proactive optimization and targeted AD are enabled within the DS-RAN-XAP framework.

B. Experimental Setup and Results

We proceed with presenting the experimental setup and results for the classification task. First, we label 4G samples with the "1" label (positive class) and 5G samples with the "0" label (negative class). The resulting training dataset comprises 41902 samples, half from each class, across all 12 KPIs, with an 80-20% train-validation split. All tested models are trained on this training dataset. The trained models are then tested and compared across all samples of the true and predicted windows \mathbf{X}_{out} and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{out}}$, each with $W \times H = 297 \times 120 = 35640$ distinct samples. Regarding the training process parameters, for the tree-based models (RF, XGBoost, LGBM), we run a grid search for hyperparameter tuning among different parameter sets and select the best-performing set for each model. The CNN classifier comprises a single 1-dimensional convolutional layer of 32 units, along with fully-connected layers, while the MLP classifier comprises only fully connected layers. Both neural network models are trained for 50 epochs with the *binary_crossentropy* loss, Adam optimizer, and a learning rate of 0.001. Dropout and early stopping are also applied to avoid overfitting.

As the class labels of the test set are imbalanced, to evaluate the classification, we use the F1 score, Precision, and Recall metrics, which are appropriate for evaluating binary classification tasks and are defined as follows:

$$Pre = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, Rec = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, F1 = \frac{2 \times Pre \times Rec}{Pre + Rec} \quad (9)$$

where True Positives (TP) are samples that belong in the positive class that the model correctly classified as positive, False Positives (FP) are samples of the negative class that the model incorrectly classified as positive, and False Negatives (FN) are samples that belong in the positive class that the model incorrectly classified as negative.

The classification evaluation metrics for all compared models are presented in Table IV, for both the true (left

side of the Table) and forecasted (right side of the Table) test samples. The results indicate that performance is compelling, reaching an F1 score of 89.2% on the true test set.

One significant outcome of our comparative analysis is that the tree-based models outperform the neural network models in almost all cases, while also being far more computationally efficient. This showcases the effectiveness and applicability of simpler models for AI-enabled tasks in the resource and power-constrained RAN domain.

As expected, the average performance in the predictive workflow, which is calculated as the average across all timesteps of H , is slightly worse. For a more detailed view of how the forecasting horizon affects the results, we provide Fig. 4 that depicts the F1 scores of all compared models, calculated across the timesteps of the forecasted windows. As depicted, for the first 15-20 seconds, the predictive classification performance remains consistently high. Between timesteps 20 and 50, there is a gradual degradation, however, the best-performing models provide usable accuracy close to 75-80%. After timesteps 70-80, performance starts dropping more noticeably. Overall, we validate that DS-RAN-XAP's predictive classification process is feasible, particularly for short- to medium-range horizons, thus providing real benefit for proactive connectivity management and planning in next-generation mobile networks.

TABLE IV
4G VS 5G CLASSIFICATION RESULTS FOR TRUE AND FORECASTED TEST SAMPLES

Model	F1	Pre	Rec	F1_pred	Pre_pred	Rec_pred
LR	0.619	0.496	0.824	0.574	0.459	0.764
RF	0.882	0.841	0.927	0.691	0.631	0.762
XGB	0.886	0.834	0.946	0.685	0.632	0.747
LGBM	0.892	0.849	0.939	0.683	0.619	0.761
CNN	0.814	0.733	0.915	0.686	0.628	0.755
MLP	0.802	0.715	0.913	0.666	0.579	0.783

Fig. 4. F1 scores for 4G vs 5G classification across the timesteps of the forecasting horizon in the predictive workflow.

Regarding the explainable output of the process, we use the *TreeExplainer* module of SHAP to calculate the feature importance values and create an explainability summary plot that provides a global overview of KPI importance and impact on a model's output. In SHAP summary plots,

the Y-axis orders KPIs by overall importance from top to bottom, and the X-axis depicts the Shapley values. Positive values indicate features pushing the prediction towards the positive class, while negative values towards the negative class. Red points represent high KPI original values, while blue points represent low KPI original values.

Fig. 5 presents the summary global explainability plot for the best-performing model in the classification task, which is LGBM. Based on this plot, Longitude, Latitude, and NRxRSRQ are identified as the most influential features overall. However, the low or high values of these KPIs do not push the model consistently toward a specific class. This suggests that their influence is more contextual, depending on the specific location or cell-level configuration, and highlights their role in capturing regional connectivity behavior rather than RAT-specific differences.

On the contrary, other features appear slightly less important but offer more detailed explanations relevant to the underlying mobile network. High CQI and RSRP values are associated with 5G connectivity, while low Downlink bitrate values appear linked to 4G. This output reflects the improved signal quality and better modulation and coding schemes of 5G.

Further, high values of RSRQ push model decisions to the 4G class, and low values push decisions to the 5G class. This can indicate relatively high congestion in 5G cells, as RSRQ often degrades when a large number of Resource Blocks are in use.

This interpretable model output helps strengthen confidence in the classifier's internal logic, but also provides utility to DS-RAN-XAP by allowing operators and UE users to understand and validate the model's decisions. This transparency and trust are necessary towards the operational adoption of AI-enabled frameworks for beyond 5G networks.

Fig. 5. SHAP global explainability summary plot of LGBM model for 4G vs 5G classification. Location features have the highest overall impact. CQI, RSRQ, Downlink bitrate, RSSI and RSRP appear slightly less impactful, but are each linked to a specific RAT class, offering insights into the underlying mobile network.

VII. STAGE 2: UNSUPERVISED EXPLAINABLE ANOMALY DETECTION

This Section presents the second part of the dual-stage pipeline, which focuses on unsupervised explainable AD. This stage enables proactive and interpretable detection of connectivity degradations, which is essential for ensuring reliability in 5G and future 6G systems. We first describe the methodology used to train and apply the proposed AE-based model with SHAP explanations, and then present the corresponding experimental results that validate its performance.

A. Methodology

In this stage, we focus on identifying abnormal connectivity behavior in an unsupervised manner to incorporate fine-grained diagnostic capability into the framework, extending beyond the classification of the previous stage. Detecting performance anomalies at the RAN level is crucial for proactively identifying issues like unusual radio conditions or unexpected throughput patterns. These anomalies may not always correlate with RAT shifts detected in the classification process, but can indicate subtle connection degradations or abnormal network states that require further analysis. Building on the outputs of the forecasting and classification stages, to achieve effective unsupervised AD, we select a reconstruction-based approach by employing a stacked AE architecture. Such models have been successfully applied to various AD tasks in mobile networks [22], [23], [45].

The AE architecture we devised for the framework consists of: (i) an Encoder comprising two fully-connected layers, that compresses the input sample $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] \in \mathbb{R}^n$ into a lower-dimensional latent space representation $z = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_d] \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and (ii) a symmetrical Decoder that is trained to reconstruct the input from the latent representation. We train the model to minimize the reconstruction MSE loss between input and output, which, similarly to (7), can be defined for each input sample as:

$$MSE_{AE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 \quad (10)$$

where x is the original input vector, $\hat{x} = [\hat{x}_1, \dots, \hat{x}_n]$ is the reconstructed output from the decoder, and n is the number of features. This loss represents the reconstruction error between the original and reconstructed data. When trained only on high-quality 5G connectivity samples, the AE learns a representation of the desired connectivity status. During inference, unseen or abnormal samples are expected to have higher reconstruction errors due to their deviation from the training dataset.

To define this training dataset, we leverage the explainable classification results from Section VI. Specifically, SHAP-based global feature importances identified RSRP, CQI, and DL bitrate as strong indicators of high-quality 5G connectivity. These SHAP computations provide data-driven insights into KPI interactions, revealing how these metrics collectively point to underlying network behavior (e.g.,

elevated RSRP and CQI correlating with stable connection, while lower values indicate 4G fallback or degradation). This guides an informed heuristic process, augmenting domain knowledge with experimentally validated attributions to define normal conditions more precisely than unguided methods. Specifically, we select training samples with above-average values in the KPIs identified through the SHAP analysis as highly linked with 5G conditions, by computing percentile limits across the 5G-labeled data. In particular, we retain only the samples for which RSRP and CQI exceed the 60th percentile and DL bitrate exceeds the 50th percentile, concurrently. These values are chosen empirically to balance strict signal quality criteria with sufficient training set size, and can be tuned according to network conditions or QoS requirements. We also filter out instances with very low SNR to ensure robust signal conditions. The resulting samples form a reliable dataset for training the AE model to learn the normal connectivity conditions. In the absence of SHAP analysis, defining the normal set would rely on variance-based feature selection or purely heuristic thresholds derived from domain expertise alone, lacking direct experimental validation. This would alter the anomaly distribution and reduce the framework's adaptability to changing network dynamics.

Finally, we also incorporate explainability into this stage by applying the SHAP *KernelExplainer* module to the AE's reconstruction loss. Kernel Explainer is a model-agnostic application of SHAP that can be used to interpret custom deep learning architectures. Specifically, we define a dedicated wrapper model that returns the reconstruction error of the trained AE for each input sample. By applying *KernelExplainer* to this wrapper of the AE, we can generate local feature importance explanations for the reconstruction error of each sample. This allows us to identify which KPIs contribute most to each detected anomaly. This explainability step provides human-interpretable insight into the root cause of each anomaly, facilitating operator and user trust, as well as the mitigation of abnormal network behavior.

In summary, this stage enhances DS-RAN-XAP's capability to detect subtle or emerging issues in the RAN, supports proactive monitoring strategies, and fosters trust in the AI pipeline through interpretable outputs.

B. Experimental Setup and Results

Regarding the experimental setup, first, we list the specific architecture and parameters for training the AE model. Following the AE's input layer, the Encoder comprises two fully connected layers with ReLU activation function, the first with 16 units and the second with 8 units, each followed by a Batch Normalization layer and a Dropout layer of 0.2. The symmetrical Decoder also comprises two fully connected layers with ReLU function, the first with 8 units followed by Batch Normalization and a 0.2 Dropout, and the second with 16 units, only followed by Batch Normalization. Finally, the output fully connected layer has 12 units, equal to the number of input features, to effectively reconstruct

input samples, with a linear activation function. The model is trained for 100 epochs with the Adam optimizer, learning rate of 0.001, validation split of 0.1, and early stopping.

The trained AE is tested on both the true and forecasted KPI windows \mathbf{X}_{out} and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{out}}$, similarly to the previous stage, to detect deviations in connectivity patterns. As in most open-source RAN-level datasets, there are no explicit anomaly labels available in the selected dataset, which makes direct supervised evaluation of the AD task performance infeasible. To address this, we employ an alternative evaluation strategy based on comparing the anomalies detected across real and predicted data, which provides an estimate of how well the AE generalizes in the forecasting-aware workflow. We calculate the metrics defined in (9), where in this case TP are samples identified as anomalous in both the ground truth data and forecasted data, FP are samples flagged as anomalous in the forecasted data but not in the ground truth data, and FN are samples identified as anomalous in the ground truth data but missed in the forecasted data.

To determine which samples are flagged as anomalies, we define specific anomaly thresholds. These thresholds are defined as percentile values of the reconstruction error distribution computed on the normal training set. A grid search is conducted across threshold ranges for both the ground truth and forecasted data, and the pair of thresholds that yields the highest F1-score is selected. This ensures balanced detection sensitivity for both data streams. These thresholds can be tuned based on the dataset, target RAN conditions, and desired AD sensitivity. Table V presents the selected thresholds and the evaluation metrics for the AD task across full (120-step) and medium (40-step) prediction horizons. Additionally, Fig. 6 depicts the average F1-score across the full horizon. Based on the results, the model achieves an F1-score close to 80% for the first timesteps, followed by a gradual decline as the horizon increases. Given the fine-grained and complex nature of the unsupervised AD task at the RAN level, these results indicate a reasonably strong performance of the model in a forecasting-aware setting. This validates the viability of our framework for proactive medium-term detection of abnormal connectivity behavior in real-world mobile network environments.

TABLE V
AE-BASED ANOMALY DETECTION EVALUATION RESULTS

Metric	120 Steps	40 Steps
Number of Samples in the AE training dataset	4612	
Anomaly Threshold (True test set)	95%	
Anomaly Threshold (Forecasted test set)	91.5%	
F1-Score	0.689	0.756
Precision	0.682	0.780
Recall	0.696	0.733

We continue with presenting the outputs of the framework regarding explainability in the AD process. To depict the SHAP results, we randomly select a 60-timestep region that was flagged as anomalous in both the true and forecasted test datasets. Fig. 7 depicts the SHAP val-

Fig. 6. AE average F1-score across the 120-step prediction horizon. The model maintains high predictive anomaly detection performance in early steps, gradually degrading at later timesteps.

ues computed over the reconstruction error for the true and predicted data. Although the SHAP value distributions exhibit slight variance, both consistently identify low values of CQI, RSRQ, SNR, and RSRP as the dominant contributors to the detected anomaly. This consistency supports the framework’s ability to identify key contributors to abnormal behavior in both the direct and predictive workflows. Fig. 8 showcases the true ground truth values of these KPIs around the anomalous region. All four KPIs exhibit local minima during this interval, confirming an existing degradation in channel quality and supporting the validity of the SHAP analysis. This explainable output enables targeted mitigation by tying anomalous KPIs to specific actions. For example, low CQI or low RSRQ causing an anomaly can be mitigated by beamforming or modulation adjustments, while identifying a degraded RSRP as the cause can be linked to handover suggestions. Overall, the results validate that SHAP integration facilitates real-time and predictive anomaly mitigation, enhancing the operational reliability of DS-RAN-XAP.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this work introduced DS-RAN-XAP, an explainable anomaly prediction framework for multivariate RAN telemetry. The framework addressed a critical gap in the transition from 5G to 6G systems, by integrating forecasting, explainable classification, and unsupervised AD into a unified pipeline. This targets an important advancement from reactive monitoring in today’s networks to the proactive management required for 6G. Additionally, by integrating explainability throughout the framework, we advance the shift toward trustworthy and actionable network intelligence.

Experimental results on real-world UE-side RAN data demonstrated the framework’s effectiveness in real-time and predictive workflows. The framework achieved an F1-score of 89.2% in the real-time RAT classification task, while also maintaining high accuracy in predictive classification for medium and longer forecasting horizons. The AE-based AD component achieved an F1-score of 75% over medium-term prediction windows, validating its capacity to identify channel degradations in both true and forecasted data. SHAP integration across the classification and AD stages enhanced transparency, enabling root-cause analysis and mapping RAN KPI values to specific connection quality. The

(a) SHAP values for True data

(b) SHAP values for Forecasted data

Fig. 7. SHAP values calculated for the selected detected anomaly for (a) true and (b) predicted data. In both cases, CQI, RSRQ, SNR, and RSRP are identified as the main contributors to the anomaly, as low values of these KPIs increase the reconstruction error.

modular structure of DS-RAN-XAP further allowed flexible model selection at each stage, supporting adaptation to diverse network deployments and operational goals.

Future work will focus on generating a UE-side RAN-level dataset with labeled anomalies to enable direct performance evaluation of the presented AD approaches. We also plan to deploy DS-RAN-XAP in a 6G experimentation facility to evaluate its closed-loop effectiveness for AD by applying real-time mitigating actions based on the provided SHAP insights.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was co-funded by the European Union 6G-BRICKS project under Grant Agreement No. 101096954 and by the European Union SUNRISE-6G project under Grant Agreement No. 101139257. This work was also supported in part by the Spanish Ministry of Science with ERFD funds under project PID2022-142105OB-I00.

Fig. 8. True values of the identified contributing KPIs around the detected anomaly. The local minima confirm channel quality degradation in the anomalous interval.

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